

BIO-INSPIRED MICROSTRUCTURE DESIGN TO IMPROVE TRANSLAMINAR FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF THIN-PLY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we used micro-cuts perpendicular to the fibre direction to promote the formation of bundle pull-outs during translaminar fracture and hence increase the translaminar fracture toughness in thin-ply composite laminates. In order to achieve this, an analytical model based on shear-lag was developed predict the probability of the micro-cuts resulting on the formation of bundle pull-outs. A manufacturing technique based on a laser engraving process was then developed to create high precision patterns of micro-cuts in un-cured single thin-ply laminae. Finally, the concept was validated through an experimental parametric study on different geometries of micro-cut patterns. The patterns of micro-cuts proved effective in deflecting the crack during translaminar crack propagation and promoting the formation of large bundle pull-outs, depending on the bundle length as predefined by the geometry of the pattern. The experimental results showed good agreement with the analytical model.

1 INTRODUCTION

A sound understanding of the toughening mechanisms in fibre-reinforced composites is fundamental for damage tolerant designs. Visual examination of the translaminar fracture surface of these materials reveals a hierarchical organization of fibre pull-outs, where single fibres are pulled out of small bundles, which in turn are pulled out of larger bundles [1,2]. These features are statistically self-similar and repeat themselves over different hierarchical levels, creating a quasi-fractal fracture structure [3].

Pimenta and Pinho [4] developed an analytical model for the translaminar fracture toughness of composites based on a hierarchical failure mechanism and a quasi-fractal structure of bundle pull-outs. The fracture toughness is computed from the energy dissipated by debonding and by friction during the pull-outs formation. The model was successfully validated against experimental data for different Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP). This demonstrates that the energy dissipated during the formation of hierarchically arranged bundle pull-outs is the main toughening mechanism in fibre-reinforced composites.

The fracture mechanisms of fibre-reinforced composites present several similarities with those of biological composites with a structural function such as shell, nacre, bone tissue and tooth enamel [5–8]. In particular, biological composites exhibit remarkable values of toughness when compared to their constituent phases and they often show a hierarchical organization of the fracture surface. Moreover, debond-

Figure 1: Crack propagation in a thin-ply composite lamina with pattern of micro-cuts perpendicular to the fibre direction: (a) before crack propagation, (b) crack propagation with bundle pull-out, (c) crack propagation with bundle failure.

ing and friction at the interfaces are some of the most important mechanisms for energy dissipation in these materials.

In biological composites, the ability to deflect and guide cracks is considered a key factor to achieve high toughness [9–11], and hinges on a discontinuous organization of the microstructure. Hard inclusions are staggered in a highly ordered architecture, and load transfer is achieved by shear stress at the interfaces. In these discontinuous microstructures, cracks tend to propagate more easily along the interfaces and around the hard inclusions [12]. This mechanism induces the crack to follow tortuous paths and promotes the formation of complex pull-outs geometries.

In this work, we draw from the theoretical understanding of the role of hierarchy in fibre pull-outs [13] and from biomimetics, in order to promote the formation of additional levels of bundle pull-outs during the fracture process of fibre-reinforced composites. The objective is to increase energy dissipation and consequently translaminal fracture toughness. This is particularly important for thin-ply composites, as the translaminal fracture toughness has been shown to decrease substantially with ply thickness [14].

To achieve this objective, we induce crack deflection and bundle pull-out through a pattern of carefully-positioned micro-cuts perpendicular to the fibre direction (Figure 1(a)). It is expected that the presence of these micro-cuts may change the translaminal fracture mechanism in the ply. If the micro-cuts are sufficiently close to the original fracture surface, they will be pulled-out (Figure 1(b)); otherwise they will not affect the fracture process (Figure 1(c)).

Figure 2: Tensile stress profile in bundle of fibres during translaminal crack propagation.

In Section 2, we briefly summarise a new model [15] which allows us to predict the probability of bundle pull-out as a function of the geometry of the pattern of micro-cuts. We then use the model to obtain these predictions for a thin-ply composite material, thereby designing patterns with different predicted probabilities of bundle pull-out for an experimental test campaign.

To experimentally insert a patten of micro-cuts in thin-ply composites, we developed a manufacturing technique involving the simultaneous laser-engraving of the pattern and of alignment features on uncured individual prepreg plies with subsequent laying-up and cure in autoclave. The manufacturing and testing procedure are detailed in Sections 4 and 5.

The experimental results are shown to compare very favourably with the modelling predictions (Section 6), thus creating a realistic possibility for exploiting the design of the fracture surface to increase the translaminal fracture toughness in fibre-reinforced composites (Sections 7 and 8).

2 ANALYTICAL MODEL TO CALCULATE PROBABILITY OF BUNDLE PULL-OUT

Figure 2 shows a bundle of length ℓ and width w , included in a ply of thickness t , in the proximity of an approaching translaminal crack. During crack propagation, the region near the crack tip experiences high tensile stress. The tensile stress, assumed to be uniform in the cross section of the bundle, is transferred to the bundle through shear stress at the interfaces. The stress is nil at the top of the bundle, where the fibres are interrupted, and maximum at the base.

If the strength of the bundle is not sufficient to withstand the tensile stress, the bundle will break and the crack will propagate through it (Figure 1(c)). The strength of a bundle of fibres is a stochastic variable as demonstrated by several experimental and numerical results in the literature [13, 16–19]. Therefore, it is not possible use a deterministic approach to identify the critical conditions for bundle failure. Instead, the probability of bundle failure (Pr^f) has to be considered.

If the strength of the bundle is sufficient to withstand the tensile stress, the bundle will survive and the crack will be forced to propagate around it, creating a bundle pull-out (Figure 1(b)). Therefore, it is possible to define the probability of bundle pull-out (Pr^{Po}) as being the reciprocal of the probability of bundle failure,

$$\text{Pr}^{\text{Po}} = 1 - \text{Pr}^f. \quad (1)$$

To calculate the probability of bundle pull-out, it is necessary determine the stress profile in the bundle and the corresponding strength distribution. The tensile stress profile in the bundle is calculated using a shear lag analysis which assumes elastic perfectly plastic behaviour of the matrix. The strength distribution of the bundle is calculated using the Hierarchical Fibre Bundle Model (HFBM) developed by

Figure 3: Analytical probability of bundle pull-out as a function of the bundle length ℓ and for different values of bundle width w .

Pimenta and Pinho [13]. The complete development of the method used to calculate Pr^{Po} is described in detail by Bullegas et al. [15].

The probability of bundle pull-out depends on the geometry of the bundle but also on the properties of the material (fibres and matrix). Figure 3 shows the variation of Pr^{Po} as a function of the bundle length ℓ , for different values of the width w and considering a thin-ply carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (TR50s/K51) produced by Skyflex [20].

It is important to notice that Pr^{Po} decreases with the bundle length. In fact, longer bundles are statistically weaker and also subjected to higher tensile stress. The model also predicts wider bundles to be more resistant and to create longer pull-outs. This is due to the fact that, under the assumptions of the model, wider bundles experience a lower tensile stress and this effect is more significant than the change of strength with w .

3 DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS

By defining patterns with different geometrical parameters ℓ and w (Figure 4(a)), it is possible to perform an experimental parametric study on the effect of the bundle length and width on the probability of pull-out. Based on the results presented in Figure 3, five different values of the parameter w were selected, ranging from 0.025 mm up to 0.5 mm. For each value of w , eight different values of the parameter ℓ were selected, ranging from 0.025 mm up to 2 mm. Therefore, 40 different patterns were defined (Table 1). The distance between the micro-cuts in all patterns is arbitrarily set to a large value ($p = 5w$ in Figure 4(a)) to avoid interaction between different bundles.

Six Compact Tension (CT) specimens were designed to test the behaviour of the patterns during crack propagation (Table 2) using a symmetric cross-ply lay-up ($[(90, (0, 90)_{20}]_s$) with forty 0° plies. Each 0° ply in each specimen contains a pattern of micro-cuts which repeats uniformly along the test section of the specimen. By having a different pattern (different combination of the parameters w and ℓ) in each ply, while keeping a symmetric lay-up, it is possible to test up to 20 different patterns in each CT specimen.

Two CT specimens (SP1 and SP2) were defined without any pattern of micro-cuts so that they are used as a baseline reference for the material behaviour. The other four CT specimens are divided in pairs

Figure 4: Representation of the specimens manufacturing process: (a) schematic representation of laser engraved pattern, (b) patterns locations in the single ply, (c) lay-up process, (d) specimens cut from the final laminate

of twin specimens containing the same 20 patterns, but in different positions of the lay-up. This allows us to compare the behaviour of the same pattern in different positions across the thickness. The distribution of the patterns contained in the four CT specimens is defined in Table 1 and in Table 2.

Table 1: Combinations of values of w and ℓ used in the parametric study

bundle width w [mm]	bundle length ℓ [mm]							
	0.025	0.025	0.05	0.075	0.1	0.125	0.15	0.175
0.05	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.2	0.25	0.3	0.35	0.375
0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.55	0.6	0.65
0.2	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.1
0.5	0.25	0.5	0.75	1.0	1.25	1.5	1.75	2.0
Specimens:	SP3 & SP4				SP5 & SP6			

Table 2: Distribution of patterns in the specimens

Specimens	Patterns
SP1	none
SP2	none
SP3	$w = 0.025 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 0.025 \text{ mm} \rightarrow w = 0.5 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 1.0 \text{ mm}$
SP4	$w = 0.025 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 0.025 \text{ mm} \rightarrow w = 0.5 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 1.0 \text{ mm}$
SP5	$w = 0.025 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 0.125 \text{ mm} \rightarrow w = 0.5 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 2.0 \text{ mm}$
SP6	$w = 0.025 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 0.125 \text{ mm} \rightarrow w = 0.5 \text{ mm} \ \& \ \ell = 2.0 \text{ mm}$

4 MANUFACTURING

A 200 mm by 250 mm cross-ply laminate panel ($[90, (0, 90)_{20}]_s$) was manufactured using hand lay-up. The material system used is the mentioned UD carbon-epoxy prepreg (TR50s/K51) produced by Skyflex [20], which comes in two grades: grade A has nominal ply thickness of 0.03 mm; grade B has a nominal ply thickness of 0.05 mm. The thinner prepreg was used for the 0° plies, while the thicker prepreg was used for the 90° plies, to promote better isolation of the failure mechanisms in the different 0° plies.

Before lamination, each of the 0° plies in the laminate was separately machined and engraved with a different pattern of micro-cuts in six locations (figure 4(b)). A laser micro-milling machine (Oxford Lasers, Series A) was used to create the patterns of micro-cuts in the 0° plies. The laser machine produces a laser beam which is able to vaporize the material locally, creating a clean cut with thickness of $\cong 15 \mu\text{m}$. Each pattern is preceded by an initial 5 mm straight cut (laser-cut notch, Figure 4(a)), which is realised together with the pattern using the laser engraving technique.

Four alignment holes were also created in each ply by the laser at the same time as the patterns. The pin-holes were then used during the lay-up process to align the plies and guarantee perfect overlapping of patterns in corresponding locations in the final laminate. The order of the patterns across the laminate was defined by the parametric study described in Section 3.

After curing in accordance to the manufacturer specification [20], a CNC water-jet machine was used to cut the plate into the specimens geometry (specimens SP1 to SP6 in Figure 4(d)). The same pin-holes alignment system was used to guarantee the coincidence of the locations of laser-cut notch and patterns in the laminate with the test section of the correspondent CT specimen. The CT specimens contain a water-jet cut notch which terminates with a blunted semicircular shape (Figure 4.d). This intercepts the initial point of the laser-cut notch engraved in each 0° ply.

Specimens SP2 and SP6 were damaged during the water-jet cutting procedure and it was not possible to test them.

5 TESTING

A total of four CT specimens (SP1, SP3, SP4, SP5) were tested using an Instron load frame with a 10 kN load cell; each specimen was loaded under displacement control at a rate of 0.5 mm/min. A video strain gage system was used to measure and record the relative displacement of two target points drawn on the surface of the specimens (Figure 5).

Measurements of load were recorded via the Instron load frame and synchronized with the relative displacement of the two target points measured by the video strain gage system. The test was stopped

Figure 5: Crack propagation during compact tension test. In the magnified portion of the specimen, it is possible to notice clearly how the initial notch acts as a crack initiator.

when the cross-head displacement reached 3 mm. At the end of each test, the specimen was wedged before unloading in order to prevent crushing of the fracture surface.

6 RESULTS

During tensile testing, the stress concentration at the end of the water-jet cut notch caused the opening of the laser-cut notch, which then acted a crack initiator as shown in Figure 5. The crack then propagated uniformly across the thickness of the specimen as shown in Figure 6. Since the laser-cut notch was realised together with the patterns of micro-cuts, this led to a precise alignment of the crack propagation plane and the patterns.

The fracture surface of the specimens is characterized by the presence of large bundle pull-outs protruding from the 0° plies (an example is shown in Figure 6). It is important to notice that the bundle pull-outs are not disposed uniformly in the surface. In fact, it is possible to distinguish 0° plies with a regular sequence of pull-outs (as highlighted in red in Figure 6), and others where the bundle pull-outs are more sparse or not present at all.

A statistical analysis of the fracture surfaces was performed in order to compare the effect of the different pattern of micro-cuts in promoting the formation of bundle pull-outs. For each ply, the percentage of bundle pull-outs (as opposed to bundle failures) was calculated based on the SEM observation of the entire fracture surface. Note that each 0° ply was engraved with a different, and uniform, pattern of micro-cuts (different plies have different values of w and ℓ).

The results of this statistical analysis are shown in Figure 7; every data point represents the probability of pull-out for a specific pattern. The results of the analytical model presented in Section 2 are shown for comparison in dashed lines. The best approximation of the experimental results is obtained when a value of $w = 0.03$ mm is used in the model; this case is highlighted in Figure 7.

Figure 6: SEM picture of fracture surfaces: detail of bundle pull-outs in single ply (highlighted in red).

7 DISCUSSION

During the Compact Tension test, precise alignment of the crack propagation plane and the patterns of micro-cuts in the test section of the specimens was obtained. The alignment was only possible due to the simultaneous engraving of the laser-cut notch, the patterns and the alignment holes in the single ply during the manufacturing of the specimens. This condition is fundamental for the parametric study because it allows to determine with precision the length of the single bundle pull-out and it would not have been possible using a conventional notch machining technique such as sawing [14].

The results of the experimental parametric study presented in Figure 7 show a clear dependence of the probability of bundle pull-out on the bundle length ℓ , but do not show any significant dependence on the bundle width w . The experimental results correlate well with model predictions for $w = 0.03$ mm. As this value coincides with the ply thickness t , this observation suggests that, when in the presence of a notch and a strong stress gradient, it is not the total area of the bundle that determines the probability of pull-out, but rather the area of the sub-bundle with area t^2 that is closer to the crack tip.

Figure 7: Experimental probability of bundle pull-out; the data point are obtained through statistical analysis of the fracture surface. The analytical probability of bundle pull-out is plotted for comparison.

8 CONCLUSIONS

The visual analysis of the fracture surfaces (Figure 6) shows that patterns of micro-cuts perpendicular to the fibre direction can be effective in deflecting a translaminar crack and promoting the formation of large bundle pull-outs in thin-ply composites. It also confirms that the simultaneous engraving of the pattern, the laser-cut notch and the alignment features in the single lamina allows for a precise alignment of the crack propagation plane and the patterns during translaminar fracture.

The results of the statistical analysis (Figure 7) demonstrate that the probability of formation of a bundle pull-out is strongly dependent on the bundle length. Longer bundles break more frequently during translaminar fracture and create fewer pull-outs.

The comparison between the modelling and experimental results showed good agreement when the value of the parameter w is set equal to the ply thickness t . This suggests that, in the presence of large stress gradients, the strength of a bundle is governed by the strength of a sub-bundle of cross section area t^2 . When the effect of the ply thickness is correctly taken into account, the model proved capable of capturing the dependency of the pull-out probability on the bundle length.

This validated analytical model opens the possibility of actively design the structure of the translaminar fracture surface in thin-ply composites. This possibility can be exploited to maximize the energy dissipated in the pull-out process and, ultimately, to increase the translaminar fracture toughness.

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